

Thiocarbamylation of Amines by Bis-(thiocarbamyl) Disulphides*

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The reaction of bis-(methylthiocarbamyl, ethylthiocarbamyl, dimethylthiocarbamyl, and diethylthiocarbamyl) disulphides with a number of amines, leading to the formation of di- and tri-substituted thiocarbamides, has been described and the mechanism of the reaction discussed.

The classical amine-carbon disulphide reaction for the preparation of 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides has been the subject of a number of investigations¹⁻¹⁰. The reaction, depending on the experimental conditions, has been envisaged to involve intermediates, like isothiocyanates⁴, dithiocarbamates⁷, bis-(thiocarbamyl)^{8,11} disulphides, xanthates¹⁰, and thiourethanes¹⁻². Of these, the bis-(thiocarbamyl) disulphides do not appear to have been isolated, although as oxidation products of dithiocarbamates, the primary products of amine-carbon disulphide reaction, these are likely to be formed, especially when oxidising agents, like sulphur², iodine³, hydrogen peroxide⁶, or sulphur monochloride⁷ are present. Being unstable, most probably these decompose to the related isothiocyanates which combine with excess of amines present to form the related 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides¹¹.

In their interaction with dithiocarbamates, thiourethanes, and xanthates, alkyl and aryl amines show considerable individual variations¹²⁻¹⁶. For example, alkyl thiourethanes, easily formed from a xanthate and amine, are quite stable and do not further react easily with amines to form the related 1,3-disubstituted thiocarbamides¹³. Aromatic

*In the older nomenclature, these are designated as thiram disulphides.

1. Lowmitsh, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 470.
2. *Idem*, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 49.
3. Fry, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 1539.
4. Fromm, *Annalen*, 1906, 348, 144.
5. Bram, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2726.
6. Braun and Beschke, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4369.
7. Snedker, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 747.
8. Connor, "Organic Chemistry-An Advanced Treatise", edited by Henry Gilman, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., N. Y. Vol. I, 1954, p. 941.
9. Hugerhoff, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2245.
10. Nambury, Ph. D. thesis, 1960, Banaras Hindu University.
11. Of Nambury and Chaturvedi, *J. Sci. Res., B. H. U.*, 1957-58, VIII (i), 86.
12. Nambury, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 95.
13. *Idem*, *J. Vh. Univ.*, 1958, 2, 101.
14. *Idem*, *this Journal*, 1959, 35, 853.
15. Sahasrabudhey *et al.*, unpublished results.
16. Aravindanjan and Brahmaramba, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 296.

thiourethanes, on the other hand, react with aromatic amines with great ease¹⁴. Ammonium aryldithiocarbamates also do not react with any ease with amines¹⁴, whereas certain amine salts of alkylthiocarbamic acids on mere warming eliminate hydrogen sulphide and afford almost quantitative yields of the related thiocarbamides¹⁰. Since nothing was known about the interaction of amines and bis-(thiocarbamyl) disulphides, excepting the reaction of the parent bis-(thiocarbamyl) disulphide with aniline leading to a mixture of phenylthiocarbamide and thiocarbamilide¹⁷, an investigation of it with a view to assessing its usefulness for thiocarbamylation was not without interest.

A detailed and systematic investigation of the reaction of bis-(methylthiocarbamyl, ethylthiocarbamyl, dimethylthiocarbamyl, and diethylthiocarbamyl) disulphides with a variety of amino compounds has now been carried out. When heated with amines in ethanol or benzene for short intervals, the bis-(methylthiocarbamyl and ethylthiocarbamyl) disulphides afforded high yields (80-95%) of the related thiocarbamides (vide Table I). The reaction was found very fast with benzylamine, *sec.*-butylamine, and *o*- and *p*-toluidines, moderate with *p*-chloroaniline and 1- and 2-naphthylamines, and sluggish with 2-amino-benzothiazole and 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole. No reaction occurred with compounds such as diphenylamine, Hector's base¹⁸, guanidine hydrochloride, and *S*-benzylisothiuronium chloride (vide Experimental). The bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl and diethylthiocarbamyl) disulphides also reacted readily with aniline, *o*- and *p*-toluidines, benzylamine, and *p*-chloroaniline, affording the corresponding tri-substituted thiocarbamides. Reaction with naphthylamines and 2-aminopyridine was found slow and no reaction was observed with secondary amines, like methylaniline and ethylaniline, and other amino compounds, *viz.*, Hector's base, 2-aminobenzothiazole, 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, etc.

The reaction is attended in every case with evolution of hydrogen sulphide and separation of elemental sulphur which amounts to one atom per mole of the disulphide. Another general feature of the reaction is that although the reactants are colorless, the reaction mixtures invariably acquire colour ranging from yellow to red during the course of the reaction and the colour fades slowly with the progress of reaction. The colours were most pronounced in the reactions with bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl and diethylthiocarbamyl) disulphides. In the case of reactions carried out at higher temperatures (125° and 140°) with bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) disulphide, in addition to hydrogen sulphide and elemental sulphur, small quantities of tetramethylthiocarbamide and bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) sulphide¹⁹ were also detected in the reaction mixture.

Independent experiments, carried out to study the behaviour of bis-(methylthiocarbamyl) disulphide in boiling ethanol/benzene also revealed the formation of hydrogen sulphide and elemental sulphur. The cold filtrates from the experiments, when treated with aniline, afforded 1-methyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide in considerable quantities, pointing to the presence of methyl isothiocyanate in these solutions. This is in agreement with the earlier observations on the hydrolytic and pyrolytic decomposition of bis-(methylthiocarbamyl) disulphide^{18,19,20}.

17. Klason, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1887, **46**, 59.

18. Hector, *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 1176.

19. Braun, *Ber.*, 1912, **35**, 833.

20. Freund and Asbrand, *Annales*, 1895, **285**, 176.

In view of the close relationship of bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) sulphide with the disulphide and its facile formation from the latter^{21,22}, the reaction of amines with bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) sulphide was also studied.

The thiocarbamides obtained in the various experiments were identified through comparison and mixed m.p. with authentic samples prepared by other methods. Where the products were new and obtained for the first time, nitrogen or sulphur was determined to confirm their identity. The details of typical experiments are shown below.

EXPERIMENTAL

Interaction of Bis-(methylthiocarbamyl)ethylthiocarbamyl Disulphides and Amines: Formation of the Related 1-Methyl|ethyl-3-substituted Thiocarbamides.—Aniline (4.6 g., 0.05M) and bis-(methylthiocarbamyl) disulphide (5.0 g., 0.025M) were heated in ethanol (50 ml) for 1½ hr. under reflux at the bath temperature. The solution assumed a yellow colour attended with copious evolution of H₂S during the first 1 hr. and with separation of some pale yellow crystals. After 1½ hr., when the colour had faded and no more H₂S had evolved, the heating was discontinued and the reaction mixture cooled and filtered. The yellow crystals (0.6 g.) were identified as sulphur. From the filtrate, ethanol was distilled and the residue (8 g., 93%) washed with HCl(dil.). This was the crude 1-methyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide, m.p. 113-14°. On crystallisation from ethanol, colorless prisms, m.p. 115°, were obtained. It did not show any depression in m.p. when mixed with an authentic sample of 1-methyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide.

Bis-(ethylthiocarbamyl) disulphide under similar conditions afforded 1-ethyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide in 92% yield.

Most amines reacted smoothly under more or less similar conditions (Table I). No reaction occurred in the cases of diphenylamine, Hector's base, *p*-tolylguanidine, di-*o*-tolylguanidine, guanidine hydrochloride, and *S*-benzylisothiuronium chloride. The results of these experiments are summarised in Table I.

Interaction of Bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl)diethylthiocarbamyl Disulphides and Amines: Formation of the Related 1,1-Dimethyl|1,1-diethyl-3-substituted Thiocarbamides.—*p*-Toluidine (4.4 g., 0.04M), bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) disulphide (5 g., 0.02M), and benzene/ethanol (50 ml) were taken in a 100-ml r. b. flask and heated under reflux for 2 hr. at the bath temperature. The reaction mixture became reddish yellow within a few minutes of heating as in the preceding experiment and evolution of H₂S and separation of elemental sulphur were observed during the reaction. After discontinuing the heating, the reaction mixture was cooled and the sulphur separating was filtered. On distillation of the solvent and treatment of the residue with HCl (dil.), a solid (8 g. corresponding to 96.5% yield, m.p. 167°) was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 168°. This was identified as 1,1-dimethyl-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide.

21. Cf. Sahaarabudhey and Redhakrishnan, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 853.

22. Braun and Stehala, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2275.

TABLE I

1-Alkyl and 1,1-dialkyl-3-substituted thiocarbamides.

Solvent = 50 ml of benzene or ethanol. Temp. = 100° (W.B.), unless otherwise mentioned

No.	Reactants. R' + amine.	Time (hr.)	Product: Thiocarbamide.	Yield.	M.P.	Authentic m.p.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Aniline (4.5 g.)	1½	R = Me, R' = R ₁ = H, R ₂ = Ph	8.0 g.	116°	116°		
2	o-Tolidine (5.1 g.)	"	R = Me, R' = R ₁ = H, R ₂ = o-Tol	6.8	152°	152-53°		
3	p-Tolidine (")	"	R ₂ = p-Tol	0.0	124°	125-36°		
4	Benzylamine (")	"	R ₂ = Ph-CH ₂ -	9.1	74°	74°		
5	Methylamine (")	"	R = R ₁ = Me, R = H, R ₂ = Ph	8.5	114°	114°		
6	Ethylamine (5.8 g.)	"	R = Me, R' = H, R ₁ = Ph, R ₂ = Ph	8.0	66°	67°		
7	p-Chloroaniline (5.0 g.)	2	R = Me, R' = R ₁ = H, R ₂ = p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	8.0	129°			8: 16.17 16.00
8	1-Naphthylamine (6.7 g.)	3	R ₂ = 1-C ₁₀ H ₇	8.6	107°	106°		
9	2-Naphthylamine (6.7 g.)	3	R ₂ = 2-C ₁₀ H ₇	8.0	163°			
10	sec.-Butylamine (3.5 g.)	½	R ₂ = sec.-Bu	5.0	84°	84°		
11	2-Aminopyridine (4.7 g.)	1½	R ₂ = 2-pyridyl	6.0	145°	145°		8: 19.56 19.39
12	Piperidine (4.0 g.)	1	R ₁ = R ₂ = piperidyl	6.0	124°	125°		
13	Morpholine (4.2 g.)	1	R ₁ = R ₂ = morpholyl	6.1	94°			8: 20.34 20.00
14	2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole** (7.1 g.)	3f	R ₂ = 4-phenylthiazolyl	2.4	305°			N: 16.71 16.86
15	2-Aminobenzothiazole** (7.1 g.)	5	R ₂ = benzothiazolyl	4.2	391°			N: 18.64 18.86
H ₂ O + amine.								
1	Aniline (3.5 g.)	1½	R = Et, R' = R ₁ = H, R ₂ = Ph	7.0	98°	99.5°		
2	o-Tolidine (4.4 g.)	"	R ₂ = o-Tol	8.0	83°	84°		
3	p-Tolidine (")	"	R ₂ = p-Tol	8.5	93°	93°		
4	Benzylamine (6.0 g.)	"	R ₂ = Ph-CH ₂ -	9.5	102°	103°		
5	Methylamine (5.0 g.)	"	R = Et, R' = H, R ₁ = Me, R ₂ = Ph	8.0	114°	113-14°		
6	Ethylamine (5.0 g.)	"	R = R ₁ = Et, R' = H, R ₂ = Ph					
7	2-Aminopyridine (5.5 g.)	"	R = Et, R' = R ₁ = H, R ₂ = 2-pyridyl	4.0	133°	34°		8: 17.53 17.77

THIOCARBAMYLATION OF AMINES BY BIS-(THIOCARBAMYL) DISULPHIDES

TABLE I (contd.)

No. Reactants	Time. (hr.)	Product: Thiocarbamide.	Yield.	M.P.	Authentic m.p. Found, Recd.
III* + amine.					
1 Aniline (3.9 g.)	2	R ₁ =R' ₁ =Me, R ₂ =H, R ₃ =Ph	7.2 g.	132°	132°
2 <i>o</i> -Toluidine (4.4 g.)	"	" " R ₃ = <i>o</i> -Tol.	8.1	138°	138°
3 <i>p</i> -Toluidine (")	"	" " R ₃ = <i>p</i> -Tol	8.6	168°	168°
4 Benzylamine (")	1½	" " R ₃ =Ph-CH ₂	8.6	95°	95-96°
5 2-Aminopyridine** (3.9 g.)	3	" " R ₃ =2-pyridyl	4.0	101°	S: 17.77 17.68
6 2-Chloroaniline (5.1 g.)	2	" " R ₁ = <i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	7.1	151°	152°
7 1-Naphthylamine** (6.0 g.)	5	" " R ₃ =1-C ₁₀ H ₇	4.8	160°	163°
8 2-Naphthylamine** (")	"	" " R ₃ =2-C ₁₀ H ₇	4.2	185°	S: 14.04 13.9
9 <i>sec</i> -Butylamine (3.0 g.)	2	" " R ₃ = <i>sec</i> -Bu	4.1	54°	56°
IV* + amine.					
1 Aniline (3.5 g.)	2	R ₁ =R' ₁ =Et, R ₂ =H, R ₃ =Ph	-Liquid-		b.p. 162°/15 mm.
2 <i>o</i> -Toluidine (4.0 g.)	"	" " R ₃ = <i>o</i> -Tol	6.0	101°	102°
3 <i>p</i> -Toluidine (")	"	" " R ₃ = <i>p</i> -Tol	7.1	81°	81°
4 Benzylamine (")	1½	" " R ₃ =Ph-CH ₂	7.0	67°	67°
5 2-Aminopyridine (3.5 g.)	2	" " R ₃ =2-pyridyl	Liquid.		(Purata, m.p. 148°. Found S, 7.86; recd. S, 8.11)

*I, II, III and IV represent bis-(methylthiocarbamyl), ethylthiocarbamyl, dimethylthiocarbamyl and diethylthiocarbamyl disulphides (5 g. each) respectively

**No solvent was used in these experiments.

f-Temp. = 110° (oil bath).

Bis-(diethylthiocarbamyl) disulphide under similar conditions reacted with *p*-toluidine to afford 1,1-diethyl-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide in 78% yield.

The reaction was investigated with a number of amines and bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl and diethylthiocarbamyl) disulphides. In all cases, the expected tri-substituted thiocarbamides were obtained in good yields (Table I). Secondary amines, like methylaniline, ethylaniline and diphenylamine and other amino compounds, viz., 5-imino-4-phenyl-3-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (Hector's base), 2-aminobenzothiazole, 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, guanidine (hydrochloride) and *S*-benzylisothiuronium chloride failed to react. Even when the reaction was tried with these at 125° and 140°, the usual evolution of H₂S was observed and the reaction mixture was found to contain all the unchanged amine, elemental sulphur, and considerable quantities of tetramethylthiocarbamide. Besides, there was a deposit of dimethylammonium dimethyldithiocarbamate²¹, m.p. 132°, on the condenser walls.

In another experiment, when aniline (1 g.) was heated with excess of bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) disulphide (5 g.) in benzene and the product carefully fractionated, a small quantity of bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) sulphide (0.1 g., m.p. 107°) was obtained.

Thermal Decomposition of Bis-(methylthiocarbamyl) Disulphide.—Bis-(methylthiocarbamyl) disulphide (3 g.), when heated under reflux in ethanol/benzene (50 ml) for 1½ hr., evolved H₂S and deposited elemental sulphur. After removing sulphur (0.5 g.) by filtration, aniline (3 g.) was added to the filtrate and the mixture allowed to stand for 8 hr. On evaporation of the solvent and washing the residue with HCl(dil.), a solid was obtained (3.5 g.), m.p. 114°. This was identified as 1-methyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide.

In a blank experiment, in which a mixture of methyl isothiocyanate (2 g.), ethanol (50 ml), and aniline (3 g.) were allowed to stand for 8 hr. at the room temperature, 3.4 g. of 1-methyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide was obtained.

Interaction of Bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) Sulphide and Amines: Formation of 1,1-Dimethyl-3-substituted Thiocarbamides.—Bis-(dimethylthiocarbamyl) sulphide (5 g., 0.025*M*), aniline (4.6 g., 0.05*M*), and ethanol (50 ml) were heated under reflux for 2 hr. at the bath temperature. The reaction mixture, which was deep yellow in the beginning, became almost colorless by the end of the reaction. Evolution of H₂S was observed, but no sulphur separated. At the end of the reaction, ethanol was removed by distillation and the residue washed with HCl(dil.); yield 8.2g. (91%), m.p. 132°. It was identified as 1,1-dimethyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide.

p-Toluidine (5.1g.), benzylamine (5.1 g.), *sec.*-butylamine (3.5 g.), and 2-naphthylamine (6.7 g.) under more or less similar conditions afforded 1,1-dimethyl-3-*p*-tolyl-, 1,1-dimethyl-3-benzyl-, 1,1-dimethyl-3-*sec.*-butyl- and 1,1-dimethyl-3-(2-naphthyl)-thiocarbamides (9.7g., 95%, m.p. 168°; 9.8g. 96%, m.p. 95°; 4.0 g., 72%, m.p. 54°; 4.3 g., 41%, m.p. 184°) respectively.

ouly challenged the earlier belief that disulphides undergo facile radical scission into sulphenyl radicals of some life. Even the thermochromism exhibited by some of the disulphides has been suggested to be due to the thermal broadening of the spectrum and not due to a reversible dissociation into sulphenyl radicals²⁴. In the light of these facts and in view of the resemblance of bis-(dialkylthiocarbonyl) disulphides with other disulphides in their reactivity towards nucleophiles, we are inclined to believe that their reaction with amines, which are typical nucleophiles, follows an ionic path rather than the one involving radical species. Following reaction mechanism is suggested:

The mechanisms outlined above account for all the observed facts. We have not, however, found a satisfactory explanation for the failure of the reaction in the case of amino compounds, such as guanidines, Hector's base, *S*-benzylisothiouronium chloride, etc.

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